

ClinicAppChain: a Low-Cost Blockchain Hyperledger Solution for Healthcare

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Abstract. Unified access to anonymous records through a trustworthy system is needed in our increasingly globalised world that still suffers from profoundly disconnected health care services. Emergencies are followed by redundant, costly and slow medical examinations without a global health data sharing mechanism. We establish the foundations of a decentralised healthcare ledger where patients decide what to share, with who, and with minimal costs. We review the state-of-the-art of transparent, auditable and interactive Blockchain-based healthcare studies, developing ClinicAppChain. Our solution features authentication, confidentiality and permissioned data sharing, considering the EU data protection regulation of 2018. ClinicAppChain is a cross-platform low-cost Blockchain prototype that empowers patients, hospitals, researchers, pharmaceuticals and insurance industries without crypto-currencies involved, and with a negligible energy foot-print (7.7 watts per node).

Keywords: blockchain, hyperledger, healthcare, low-cost, low-power

1 Introduction

Healthcare is a field that requires an efficient and secure system for managing medical records and tracking complex worldwide transactions. In this paper, we explore the feasibility of a Borderless *Electronic Health Records* (EHR) Management System using blockchain technology. Blockchain is a distributed ledger of events, transactions or electronic records, which are cryptographically secured, impossible to clone, and can evolve through a consensus protocol. Each connected node works with that consensus [14]. Despite the popular focus on financial services, Blockchain has the potential to reshape how healthcare systems currently operate, empowering users (e.g., patients, practitioners, researchers) and fomenting improved medication, disease prevention, treatments and lifestyle tracking.

Depending on the consensus algorithm, there could be a tremendous energy foot-print of high-power demanding computing systems and scalability issues [11]. For instance, the culprit of the Bitcoin power demand is its consensus algorithm, *Proof of Work* (PoW) [15]. *Proof of Stake* (PoS) algorithm came as

an alternative PoW, replacing the intensive computational work with a random selection process. It can be used both in public and private blockchains. One of the most successful blockchain platforms, Ethereum, plans to migrate from PoW to PoS. Voting-based or consensus algorithms as *Practical Byzantine Fault Tolerance* (PBFT) are preferred in private and semi-trusted environments. These algorithms require that the majority of the network be trustworthy and may suffer from message overhead as the network size increases [2].

Another issue is the cost (time and money) that healthcare providers are willing to accept to use a completely new paradigm in EHR management, as the industry is typically unwilling to invest money in supercomputers and in adopting new systems [8]. On top of all this, the European Union's *General Data Protection Regulations* (GDPR) of 2018 complicates the scenario.

A Blockchain ledger is permissioned or permissionless [14]. Permissionless means public: anyone can participate and the network is transparent. Permissioned means private: all participants are known and the network has restricted access. As healthcare deals with personal data, we need a permissioned one. Permissioned blockchains have desirable features for implementing modern EHRs [12]:

- **Decentralised:** Peer-to-peer (i.e., non-intermediated, P2P) architecture.
- **Smart Contracts:** A smart contract outlines the terms of relationships between peers with cryptographic code.
- **Immutable audit trail:** Trackable and timestamped patient-generated data.
- **Data provenance:** Evidenced source of medical research data.
- **Security/anonymity:** Patients control consent statements of their anonymously stored data, while confident that the network holds them securely.

There are various opportunities for blockchain-based applications in healthcare. Concretely, we can apply it to: (1) Longitudinal EHRs based on data from distant sources and providers, (2) automated health claims adjudications, (3) automatic providers interoperability, (4) secure online patient access to global EHRs, (5) pharmaceutical supply chain managements [18], (6) tractability against counterfeit drugs industry, and (7) permissioned clinical trials and research database [13].

In this paper, we establish the foundations and develop a prototype of a low-cost, energy efficient, secure, interconnected, law compliant, and trustworthy EHRs sharing platform that empowers users. Technically speaking, ClinicAppChain³ is a prototype built over Hyperledger Fabric and Composer Blockchain Framework using standard web-technologies, allowing conventional devices (e.g., computers, laptops, smartphones) to access ClinicAppChain applications and services, and acting as nodes of the ledger. Throughout this experience, we have identified and attempted to answer the following research questions (RQs):

- **RQ1:** What are the foundations of Blockchain for healthcare?
- **RQ2:** How can media (e.g., images, videos...) be efficiently stored and interconnected with a Blockchain ledger considering the GDPR'18?
- **RQ3:** Do we have the technology to build a sustainable and low-cost Blockchain solution for EHRs management in healthcare?

³ <https://www.clinicappchain.com>

This paper presents the following structure. In section 2 we review the state-of-the-art of current Blockchains for healthcare (RQ1). Then, we cope with data and media storage, legal aspects, compatibility (RQ2). In section 3 we propose a model of a ledger for EHRs (RQ2), develop the prototype ClinicAppChain, and evaluate its energy footprint and costs (RQ3). In section 4 we summarise the main conclusions and future work.

2 Related Work

Professional Blockchain projects are often built upon solid Blockchain frameworks [10], where the most mature in 2019, ordered by popularity are⁴:

1. **Ethereum** [19]: Widely known by its crypto-currency name (ETH) due to the popularity among the investors. It currently has the largest number of use-cases available. It is a permissionless P2P PoW (i.e., mined) based platform, which, like Bitcoin, is slow, energy-greedy, and needs high computation power, but is now switching to PoS, making it fit for private blockchains.
2. **Hyperledger Fabric** [3]: Hyperledger is an industrial grade framework with 185+ supporting companies of various industries, such as finance, supply chain management, Internet of Things, and manufacturing (e.g., The Linux Foundation, IBM, Intel). Fabric is its permissioned Business-to-Business (B2B) Blockchain Module, where peers can be grouped into organisations, and several concurrent ledgers can co-exist. It has no token or crypto-currency, and requires the majority of peers to consent to validate transactions.
3. **R3 Corda** [4]: Corda is a framework for the financial industry maintained by the company R3. It is a strict permissioned ledger, where just the peers involved in a transaction must validate it, clearly suited for banking and trading. Actual usage examples are HSBC and ING international banks.

Consequently, we present the most notable developments of blockchain healthcare ordered by advancements (RQs 1 & 2). **MedShare** [20] is a data sharing model between cloud service providers using Blockchain, which uses a private implementation of smart-contracts. In other words, the ledger contains permits alongside links to cloud data (e.g., EHRs), which is stored in databases or drives in their respective centres (e.g., hospitals, clinics, personal drives). This design is called *off-chain* [16,18], and it is, basically, a ledger that contains URLs to resources. **MediChain** [17] is an enterprise prototype of MedShare model. **MedRec** [6] is a proof-of-concept prototype of a Blockchain for off-chain EHRs, which uses Ethereum smart contracts. **BlochIE** [9] is a dual loosely-coupled Blockchain for healthcare data exchange, having one ledger for EHRs hosted off-chain, and another for *in-chain* personal data. Lastly, **MedicalChain** [1] and **Proof.work**⁵ are enterprise level off-chain Hyperledger Blockchain ecosystems with their own crypto-currencies (i.e., MED and PROOF) that aim to connect

⁴ Survey: dzone.com/articles/best-3-enterprise-blockchain-platforms-for-rapid-p

⁵ <https://proof.work>

insurance, healthcare providers, and research institutions for certain fees. In contrast, our solution strategically combines on-chain and off-chain storage and uses no cryptocurrency, aiming for robustness and scalability.

Off-chain design is popular because it facilitates the adoption of a new system (interoperability vs a new standard) and due to the European GDPR'18. The most important point of this law in Blockchain systems is *the right to be forgotten*. A system must accept a citizen's request for complete data removal. However, Blockchain is a persistent system, so the off-chain solution leads to broken links. The parties storing the data (e.g., clinics and hospitals), are the ones to answer to removal requests. However, the security of a system is as weak as its weakest component. A traditional centralise database is a security hole, as just traditional security measures can be applied besides Blockchain. A breach on a single database could affect lots of EHRs, but on the other hand, media (e.g., images, videos) are expensive to store on-chain. We address this problem and propose a more balanced approach by keeping everything on-chain, except for large media files. As just media is off-chain, no written information (e.g., diagnostics) is compromised.

Every ledger solution and framework has been first developed and compiled for x86 architecture due to its market-share and applications compatibility. However, the most used in production are ported to ARM architecture except Hyperledger (community efforts are carried-out unsuccessfully⁶). Nonetheless, we are discussing computational nodes. Applications (i.e., service interfaces) can be developed in any programming language with front-end capabilities, and run on any compatible device (e.g., web services in a computer, smartphone, smart-tv...). Material and electricity costs depend on the computational requirements of the nodes running the consensus algorithm (e.g., miners in Bitcoin require extremely powerfull nodes). Generalising, when crypto-currencies are involved, as they are part of the profitability of the specific service, mining is needed to generate those tokens. Even if Bitcoin is the most profitable mined crypto-currency to date, expensive hardware and electricity costs exceed the currently rewarded value [15]. Instead of crypto-currencies, Hyperledger Fabric uses *Byzantine Fault Tolerance* algorithm, distributing consensus in 3 types of peers: Endorsement (i.e., users credentials), Validation (i.e., validate transactions), and Ordering (i.e., to sort validated transactions inside blocks).

3 ClinicAppChain

ClinicAppChain is our low-cost and energy-efficient prototype for an EHR management system. Healthcare providers work under rigorous privacy requirements for sensitive data, so permissionless frameworks are not an option. We have chosen Hyperledger Fabric (Fig.1) version 1.4 because it is a fast (10k trans/sec.) and lightweight (no mining nor crypto-currencies) open source solution for permissioned Blockchains [7]. Moreover, it has a strong industrial and community

⁶ Up to date, this was the only working effort that stopped to be compatible after Fabric 1.0 (2 years ago)<https://github.com/Cleanshooter/hyperledger-pi-composer>

Fig. 1. ClinicAppChain - High-level Architecture.

support. The most important aspect of a Hyperledger implementation is the Business Network Definition (BND), which contains the data model definitions for all participants, assets, transaction logic, and access rules. The data model and access control rules are coded in *Hyperledger Composer Modelling Language*, and the transaction logic in JavaScript. Hyperledger Composer allows us to create a RESTful API for our Hyperledger system through the command line. Also, we can generate a basic user interface in Angular framework with *Yeoman*.

3.1 Blockchain Model

Patients, physicians, researchers, health insurers, pharmaceutical providers, governmental entities, are all actors (i.e., participants in a Blockchain jargon) that can potentially benefit from our EHR management system. This prototype currently focuses on just the first three actors. In Fig. 2 we illustrate the key use case scenarios in which the three actors interact with each other and the system (RQ1).

A **Patient** can request the following transactions: (i) edit *Personal Data*, which includes identification details as lifestyle habits, blood type, weight, height, allergies, and an emergency contact among others; (ii) consult the public profile of any Physician; (iii) add/remove a wearable device from its account; (iv) visualise research projects details; and, (v) grant and revoke permissions of his EHR to registered users (i.e., Physicians and Researchers). Permits can be granted/revoked collectively (to all Physicians/Researchers) or individually (to a specific Physician/Researcher).

A **Physician** can access the application to: (i) edit her *Public Profile*, including identification details, medical specialities, medical license and picture; (ii) access the EHR of a Patient in case of an accident, given that the patient is not conscious to explicitly give the consent and that the Physician is registered an emergency personnel; (iii) consult and add medical records to the EHRs of those patients that have permitted to do so; and, both patient and physician can list the spoken languages in their Personal Data and Public Profile respectively.

A **Researcher** can, (i) request the access to the EHR of any Patient; (ii) view the EHRs of Patients that have granted him access to their EHRs; and, (iii) add new research projects or modify the details of existing ones.

Fig. 2. ClinicAppChain use-case diagram. We use blue, green and grey to depict the use cases in which the Patient, Physician, and Researcher actor respectively, interact with each other and with the ClinicAppChain System

Fig. 3. ClinicAppChain general sequence diagram: Shows a typical course of interaction between a Patient (blue) and a Physician (green) in a healthcare ledger of Hyperledger

The central *asset* in ClinicAppChain is the EHR. Other assets are: Patient’s Personal Data, Physician’s Public Profile, and Research Projects. Each asset has one or more owners among the participants, and has a set of general access rules associated which limits who can do what transaction in the system. All participants need to authenticate to initiate a transaction. In Fig.3 we illustrate the most representative transaction scenarios of ClinicAppChain with a sequence diagram showing the regular interaction between a Patient and a Physician. Each transaction is recorded in the Hyperledger’s Blockchain.

Our greatest novelty is the mixed assets storage where we store text-based assets (e.g., diagnostics) on-chain, and media assets off-chain (e.g., MRI scan, X-Ray), unlike other prototypes discussed in the Related Work section (RQ2). This assures that, in case of a breach on any hospital, it only affects diagnostics’s support data. In case of a removal request, the transaction history cannot be erased, but current data-set would be blank, and old data would be totally inaccessible, as with lost Bitcoins worth 1000 million US dollars to date [5].

3.2 Evaluation

We have tested ClinicAppChain **peers** on three low-cost platforms: two virtual private servers, each featuring an AMD Opteron Processor 6176 with 2 cores @2.30 GHz and 4GB RAM, running Ubuntu Server 18.04 LTS x86_64, and a mini-PC worth 200\$, featuring an ultra low-power Intel i3-6100U @2.3 GHz Dual Core with Hyperthreading and 8GB RAM, running LUbuntu 18.04 LTS x86_64. For testing purposes, every node hosts the three peers at the same time, so any of them can perform as an endorsement, validation or ordering peer. They all match an average over the theoretical minimum value of **3.5k trans/sec**, so, a cheap low-power computer is capable enough for single peers. Regarding energy-footprint, we physically monitored the energy consumption of the mini-PC with *Watts Up? Pro*⁷, resulting in an average energy consumption of **7.7 Watts** (RQ3). Additionally, we have tested the **client** (Angular front-end) in a low-power Raspberry Pi 3B+, featuring four cores Cortex-A53 (ARMv8 x64) and 1GB of RAM and representing the low-end segment of smartphones. On this 'wimpy' architecture, ClinicAppChain exhibits a negligible delay due to the wifi connection, with peaks of energy consumption of **3 Watts**, similar to requesting a blog web-page (RQ3). As mentioned, ARM architecture is not yet supported as a peer node in a Hyperledger Fabric Network.

4 Conclusions and Future Work

We identify the building blocks of a Blockchain solution for healthcare (Figs. 1 and 2) and develop ClinicAppChain, a permissioned Hyperledger Fabric prototype for EHR management (RQ1). We propose a novel mixed on-chain/off-chain ledger data partition, complying the EU GDPR'18 (RQ2). Using Fabric framework, we have obtained a low-cost solution —nodes can run on cheap and small hardware (e.g., mini-PC, Raspberry Pi), and energy efficient — ~ 7.7 Watts per peer node, and ~ 3 Watts per client node (RQ3). As we have developed the client front-end using web-technologies as HTML/CSS/JavaScript/Angular, any device with a web browser can log-in and make requests to the ledger (cross-platform). Our planned future work comprises: (1) allowing wearables and sensors (e.g., endoscope, heart-rate sensor) to automatically add patients' information to the EHR, where the Raspberry facilitates it as it has specific PINs, Bluetooth and USB ports, (2) expanding the participant's roles, transactions and EHR complexity, and (3) evaluating the usability of ClinicAppChain for a dentistry scenario to see how it can benefit in everyday clinical practice.

5 Acknowledgements

Work by Munoz and Fuentes is supported by the projects MAGIC P12-TIC1814 and HADAS TIN2015-64841-R (co-financed by FEDER funds). Work by Constantinescu and Asenjo is supported by the project TIN2016-80920-R, funded

⁷ <https://www.vernier.com/products/sensors/wu-pro/>

by the Spanish Government. ClinicAppChain has been supported by IMFAHE Foundation-Nodal Award of 2018. We are particularly grateful to other members of the awarded team that have guided us in the sanitary side and legal aspects: Esther Herrera, Laura Timanfaya, Patricia Rodríguez and Myriam Martínez.

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